

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Seamounts of the Southeast Pacific

&

Unexplored Seamounts of the Salas y Gómez Ridge

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FKt240108	FKt240224
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	Seamounts of the Southeast Pacific	Unexplored Seamounts of the Salas y Gómez Ridge
Expedition Dates	2024/01/8 - 2024/02/11	2024/02/24 - 2024/04/04
Departure Port	Valparaiso, Chile	Valparaiso, Chile
Termination Port	Valparaiso, Chile	Antofagasta, Chile
Ocean	South Pacific Ocean	South Pacific Ocean

Map of Expeditions Locations

Figure 1: Map of the Expeditions' Location.

Figure 2. Map of the Expeditions' stations on the Salas y Gómez, Nazca, and Juan Fernández ridges, the Chilean Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), Ecologically and Biologically Significant Areas (EBSA), the proposed extended continental shelf of Chile, and the No-take and Multi-Use Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

1.1 Expeditions Overview

Seamounts play an integral role in oceanic processes and connectivity. They create complex current patterns that influence the communities living on and above them, and by providing food, shelter, and solid surfaces for attachment, seamounts function as oases for deep-sea life.

The Salas y Gómez, Nazca, and Juan Fernández ridges are extensive underwater mountain ranges formed by volcanic activity that run perpendicular to South America and stretch across more than 2,900 kilometers. The region is further isolated by major oceanographic features, including the Atacama Trench, the Humboldt Current system, and a large oxygen minimum zone (OMZ). Together, these factors create conditions that support remarkable biodiversity, making the ridges global hotspots of marine endemism where nearly half of the species are found nowhere else on Earth.

The Salas y Gómez Ridge extends from the coast of Chile to Rapa Nui (Easter Island) in the central Pacific. Like the surrounding ridge systems, it was formed through volcanism and provides essential habitat for deep-sea organisms. Its hard, rocky surfaces offer stable attachment points for sessile organisms, while the steep mountainous terrain interacts with ocean currents to deliver nutrients and food directly to benthic communities. These conditions help sustain the region's exceptionally high levels of endemic marine life.

Despite its ecological significance, 73% of this remote and underexplored region lies in the high seas beyond any national jurisdiction. As a result, the Salas y Gómez Ridge likely harbors

largely pristine and unexploited habitats with abundant biodiversity that may require international cooperation to ensure their protection before they are impacted.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
5434 SHOA: Nota No. 597 SHOA: JEMGA 13270/220 SUBPESCA: E-2023-612	Republica de Chile	Research

1.3 Expeditions Timeline

The first expedition (35 days), *Seamounts of the Southeast Pacific* (FKt240108), departed from Valparaiso, Chile, on January 8, 2024, and returned to Valparaiso, Chile, on Feb 11, 2024, with a mid-cruise port call in Robinson Crusoe.

The second expedition (40 days), *Unexplored Seamounts of the Salas y Gómez Ridge* (FKt240224), departed on February 24, 2024, from Valparaiso, Chile, and returned to Antofagasta, Chile, on April 4, 2024, with a mid-cruise port call in Rapa Nui.

1.4 Expeditions Objectives

The interaction of physical and biological forces creates distinct biogeographic regions that influence which organisms can live in a given area and how much life those environments can support. Scientists have long recognized a biogeographic boundary separating fauna between the Indo–West Pacific and the East Pacific. One of the central goals of this research was to determine whether this boundary extends into deeper waters and how deep-sea communities along the slopes of the region’s seamounts relate to ecosystems that have been more extensively studied elsewhere in the Pacific.

The first expedition in Chile focused on examining biogeographic patterns, biodiversity, and human impacts across selected seamounts of the Salas y Gómez, Nazca, and Juan Fernández ridges. The science team aimed to:

- Assess whether the biogeographic boundary observed among animals in the upper bathyal zone between the Indo–West Pacific and the East Pacific also occurs at deeper depths.
- Examine how deep-sea organisms inhabiting the lower slopes of seamounts are related to communities studied on other Pacific ridges and seamount systems.
- Create detailed bathymetric maps of seamounts, including sites located within Chilean marine protected areas.
- Investigate biodiversity and distribution patterns of large invertebrates - such as deep-sea corals, sponges, and associated fauna - as well as fishes.

- Evaluate the impacts of intensive fishing on seamount ecosystems and assess recolonization and recovery dynamics following fishing restrictions.

The following expedition built on these efforts to further understand the ecological and environmental drivers shaping seamount ecosystems in the region. The primary objectives were to:

- Identify biogeographic and depth-related boundaries among deep-sea seamount communities.
- Evaluate the environmental drivers influencing species distribution and survival.
- Characterize the physical environment and seafloor communities of the Easter Island Ecoregion in order to place them within the broader context of other ocean regions.
- Gather scientific data to support outreach efforts aimed at increasing awareness of the biodiversity and global importance of this region of the ocean.

Across both expeditions, the science teams focused on previously understudied biodiversity - including deep-sea corals, sponges, associated invertebrates, and fishes - living along the deep slopes of seamounts. Using non-destructive survey methods, researchers explored ten seamounts across the Salas y Gómez, Nazca, and Juan Fernández ridges, targeting complex topographic features that may host vulnerable seafloor communities. These observations will help compare local ecosystems with known communities across the Indo–West and East Pacific and improve understanding of connectivity across the region.

2 Expeditions Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Science

Biodiversity and Newly Discovered Species

FKt240108

Over 699 samples were collected, including megafaunal organisms, sediment push cores, and water samples at 10 seamounts across the Salas y Gómez, Nazca, and Juan Fernández ridges using ROV *SuBastian* (20 dives, S0632–S0651) and the SOI Lander (7 deployments).

Prior to the expedition, the species inventory for the Nazca area stood at 438 recorded species, and preliminary analysis indicates approximately 150 new records for the region, representing an increase of ~34%, of which an estimated 60% are potentially new to science.

Deep-sea corals and sponges were particularly diverse: more than 40 sponge morphospecies were observed (compared to only 2 formally described species previously known from the area).

Over 60 anthozoan species were collected, most of which had not been previously reported for the region. The densities and diversities of corals and sponge gardens observed are consistent with the criteria used to identify Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs).

Crustacean samples collected with the SOI Lander across 7 seamounts yielded over 1,100 deep-sea amphipod specimens, including potential new species of Eurythenes, Abyssorchomene, Stephonyx, Hirondelella, and Parallicella.

Twenty-eight seabird species were also observed throughout the expedition, including Humboldt Current endemics, oceanic migrants, and species nesting in the Desventuradas and Juan Fernández archipelagos — in what is believed to be one of the first expeditions to include a dedicated seabird and floating marine litter observer as part of the science team.

FKt240224

Over 23 ROV dives, the 4K Stereo Camera recorded over 210 hours of dive footage. Additionally, over 850 samples were collected by ROV during the 23 ROV dives; the > 1700 specimens were deposited in the Sala de Colecciones Biológicas UCN, and holotypes will go to the Museum of Natural History of Chile as new species are described.

We observed corals, macroalgae, and crustose coralline algae (CCA) to depths greater than reported in other regions. For example, the coral *Leptoseria* was observed and collected at 197 m depth, which is 25 m deeper than the deepest prior report of 172 m. CCA was observed and collected to > 350 m, deepest prior report is 312 m at Pitcairn. Macroalgae was observed and collected to > 185 m; deepest prior records are to ~170 m.

The collections from this expedition increased the number of recorded species of the region from 581 species to at least 741 species, an increase of > 24%. At the time of the expedition, we suspected >35% (50) of the at least 140 new reports were potential new species to science. These values are through Dive 666; 11 dives were left to review at the end of the expedition and are still being analyzed at the time of this report's publication.

During the expedition, at least 63 morphs of echinoderm species were observed; three genera were previously not reported to be present at the Salas y Gomez Ridge; and two species were potentially new to science. More than 40 morphs of mollusks were collected, including 18+ thought to be new species at the time of the expedition. These include the first living specimens of *Profundiconus* collected in the area, comprising a recently described new species and two potentially new ones. Additionally, these taxa belong to a Family of predatory gastropods known for their complex paralyzing toxins, which are currently being studied for their biotechnological applications.

During the expedition > 125 individual squat lobsters in 5 families, and 14 genera were collected. At the time of the expedition, of these, 11 genera were new reports for the region and at least 40 morphospecies were thought to be potential new species to science.

Amphipod traps deployed by the ROV at seven seamounts collected hundreds of deep-sea amphipod specimens, plus some shrimp, squat lobsters, fish, and a nudibranch.

Sediment samples using pushcores were collected at eight stations for subsequent analyses of macrofauna, meiofauna, bacteria, and biogeochemistry. Sediments were primarily fine and uncompacted foraminiferous oozes with samples collected at shallower stations having substantial amounts of biogenic materials (e.g., coral rubble, rhodoliths, sea urchin spines).

At least 374 individuals and 22 species of seabirds were observed during the expedition, half of which breed on the oceanic islands of Chile.

Squid observations and collections during the expedition:

- First record (observation, dive 663) for Southeast Pacific of the shiny bird squid *Ornithoteuthis volatilis* extends the range by 30° eastward and 7° southward respectively to the previously easternmost known distribution limit.
- First record (observation and collection, dive 675) for Southeast Pacific of the wonderful firefly squid *Lampadioteuthis megaleia* extends the distribution more than 40° of longitude towards the East of the known distribution of the species in the Pacific.
- First record for SyGR (observations and collections) of the flowervase jewell squid *Stigmatoteuthis hoyleii* (dive 660) and the purpleback flying squid *Sthenoteuthis oualaniensis* (rod collection on 7 March 2024), which are reported for the southeast Pacific.

Mapping

FKt240108

Over 54,928.5 km² of seafloor were mapped across the survey region, of which 43,916.1 km² (79.95%) had not been previously covered by high-resolution bathymetry data (based on GEBCO 2023).

At least three new seamounts were identified and partially mapped for the first time. Depths across the survey area ranged from 91 to 6,224 m, and backscatter values from -70 to -6.8 dB.

The ten seamounts surveyed include Seamounts SF19, SF17, SF10, SF2, SFX, SF5, the unnamed seamount informally known as “Solito,” JF6, JF1, and JF2.

Seamount “Solito” was completely mapped for the first time and formal naming procedures have been initiated through Chilean authorities and international protocols.

FKt240224

Over 78,000 km² of seafloor were mapped; most of which was mapped for the first time with a high-resolution, multi-beam echosounder system. On the 10 seamount and 2 oceanic island stations, over 37,000 km² were mapped; a total of 5 seamount stations were fully mapped; 8 seamounts and island stations had map coverage expanded, including the 5 that were fully mapped.

During the transit, 34 seamounts taller than 1000 m from the surrounding seafloor were intercepted; 14 of these were predicted by the Chile Uncharted Seamounts chart to exist, but most of the others were newly discovered; the tallest rises 2900 m.

Ecosystem Diversity

FKt240108

A variety of distinct benthic ecosystems were documented across the ten seamounts surveyed. Notably, habitats dominated by the urchin *Dermechinus* spp. were observed on the “Solito” seamount and on Juan Fernández Ridge seamounts, where accumulations of tests and dorsal spines had generated a specific type of sedimentary habitat.

Extensive cold-water coral reefs and sponge gardens were observed across multiple seamounts, particularly within the Nazca-Desventuradas and Montes Submarinos de Juan Fernández Marine Parks.

Signs of anthropogenic disturbance (longlines, lost traps, and debris) were detected mainly at seamounts located outside these protected areas.

FKt240224

Each seamount has unique species assemblages that change with depth, highlighting the need for protection of all seamounts, including those on the high seas.

Communities of habitat-forming fauna (corals and sponges) that are characteristic of vulnerable marine ecosystems were observed, highlighting the need to manage existing protected areas and develop protections on the high seas. For example, we observed a garden of glass sponges (*Poliopogon* and *Bolosoma*) at 594 m at seamount “Mayday” (High Seas, Dive 654), glass sponges (*Poliopogon* and unidentified sponge) at ~1066-1092 interspersed with Euplectellidae at 1088-1153 m at an unnamed seamount on the High Seas (Dive 657), a *Caryophyllia* microhabitat at 914 m at an unnamed seamount on the High Seas (Dive 658), large colonies of stony coral *Enallopsammia* at 1222 m on unregistered “Rock” seamount on the High Seas (Dive 661) and *Paracalyptrophora* at 654 m, 518 m, and 498 m at Rapa Nui (Dives 662, 663, and 664), red *Leiopathes* at 518 m and white *Leiopathes* at 483 m at Rapa Nui (Dive 663 and 664), mixed species coral gardens that changed in composition with depth and geomorphology at 506-546 m at Rapa Nui (Dive 664), a *Narella* coral garden at 475 m (Dive 664), and a *Stichopathes* garden at 172 m (Dive 673). Other notable observations are an abundance of commercially important fish at 101 m on Dive 673 and a shark at 166 m on Dive 673.

A total of 167 items of marine debris were observed; most were composed of plastic.

2.1.2 Innovative Technologies

FKt240224

The hyperspectral and stereo imaging system (HSI), developed by the Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute (MBARI) CoMPAS Lab and deployed with the support of Master Students of the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, was successfully tested during 10 dives totaling more than 100 hours on the seafloor. These data will enable further development in real-time 3D, hyperspectral, and 3D reconstruction. They will allow the technology team to better understand its capabilities and the integration of the outputs into science-related analysis.

2.2 Post-expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

FKt240108/FKt240224 (Indicated below if cruise-specific analyses)

Samples and data from the two expeditions were largely analyzed together, except for the MBES data and hyperspectral camera data.

Three species discovery workshops were conducted in collaboration with Ocean Census. During these workshops, experts were brought in to evaluate the samples morphologically, and subsamples were taken to isolate DNA and barcode the samples. The sequencing data is still coming in and undergoing phylogenetic analyses and quality assurance and control (QAQC). We anticipate submitting sequences to the public database as these analyses are completed; much of the delay arises from the slower process of completing the morphological analyses to submit the sequence data with accurate species assignments. Some sequences have been submitted and are in the process of submission.

We have been using annotation software and manual annotation methods to review the video and image files to complete a full inventory of the species observed during the expeditions. These analyses are ~50% complete. From an updated review of historical data in the region (1958–2019), a total of 1,010 species have been reported, with 505 associated with the Nazca Ridge and 597 with the Salas y Gómez system. During these expeditions, we have confirmed 607 species (to date) that were observed along the ridges. Corresponding habitat analysis reveals a clear variation in habitat composition, which is also reflected in faunal differences. The seamounts show high levels of stratification and biodiversity. Among these 607 species, over 100 of these are new records for Nazca and around 140 are new records for Salas y Gómez. These new records increase the known biodiversity in the region by ~25%. These data will not only be useful to scientists but to the broader community to understand the biodiversity of our planet, the intrinsic value of our oceans, and to prioritize areas for protection. We anticipate this data being used for a proposal to protect the Nazca and Salas y Gómez ridges under the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Treaty.

Analyses of the mapping data is underway and nearing completion. The data is being analyzed for geomorphological characteristics, habitat descriptions, and to inform seamount evolution. A number of new approaches to geomorphological analyses are being conducted. We anticipate these analyses to be completed in late 2026. The data is undergoing final QAQC prior to submission to public databases. A publication arising from these data from one completely mapped, new seamount has been submitted for peer review. These data will improve understanding of seamount evolution and the relationship of biodiversity patterns to habitat and geomorphological characteristics that scientists can use to better understand and predict community patterns and climate change effects.

The presence/absence data for selected fauna are being used in models to explore the climate change impacts and produce vulnerability maps. Preliminary results on Hexactinellida revealed potential vulnerability areas at the junction of the Salas y Gómez and Nazca Ridges according to different climate change scenarios (currently analyzed ssp245 and ssp370; Fig. 3). Meanwhile, communities of Hexactinellida harboring the Rapa Nui region will be less vulnerable to those

environmental impacts. These data will be essential to inform conservation and management plans.

FKt240108: Information on “Solito” seamount and Juan Fernández Ridge seamounts was incorporated into a proposal to develop new marine protected areas in Chile. In early 2026, these proposals for two new marine protected areas were approved, but are currently under review by the new administration in Chile.

FKt240108: Trophic structure analyses based on stable isotopes ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) were conducted on 368 faunal samples alongside 81 particulate organic matter (POM) filters and 17 sedimentary organic matter (SOM) samples. Inorganic nutrient concentrations (NO_3 , PO_4 , SiO_2 , NH_4 , NO_2) were quantified from 99 water samples across different depth zones. These data are being submitted to PANGAEA and BCO-DMO as analyses are finalized.

FKt240224: Analysis of high-resolution 3D seafloor mapping of the Salas y Gómez Ridge, a volcanic seamount chain in the Eastern Pacific achieved a reconstruction resolution of 3.22 mm/pixel over a site on the Mayday Guyot at 677 m depth, revealing volcanic crater-like structures with fractured and partially collapsed central zones. The resulting colorized 3D model and digital elevation model capture the interplay of volcanism, erosion, and tectonic subsidence that shaped this unique submarine landscape.

FKt240224: A documentary, *Te Moana Ora*, was produced by Claudia Berardi. It had premiers on YouTube and a number of showings in Rapa Nui, continental Chile, and internationally. It was selected for the 2025 Science Film Festival, where it showed in Brazil. This documentary told the story of a Rapa Nui participant and this expedition.

Biological collections from both expeditions are deposited and curated at the Sala de Colecciones Biológicas UCN (SCBUCN), Coquimbo, catalogued under international standards, imaged, and made accessible through GBIF via Darwin Core Archive format. Holotypes and voucher specimens are being additionally deposited at the Museo Nacional de Historia Natural de Chile. ESMOI continues to advance the creation of a high-seas MPA along the Salas y Gómez Ridge under the recently ratified BBNJ Treaty, in collaboration with the Chilean Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Senate of Chile, and the High Seas Coral Reef Coalition.

Hexactinellida Vulnerability Maps

Figure 3. Blue areas represent areas where no vulnerability has been detected. Yellow areas represent areas where habitat suitability will be decreased by more than 5%. P1 represents period time comprising 2026–2064 vs P2 2065 – 2100.

2.2.2 New Discoveries

FKt240108 new seamounts: We mapped one new seamount (“Solito”) that was explored on this expedition and two new unexplored seafloor features (one of which was more fully mapped on a subsequent expedition in July 2024). Five additional features were discovered during transits that require further exploration before naming proposals can be developed. Naming proposals may be co-developed for three additional features in the Chilean EEZ in collaboration with Chilean officials.

FKt240224 new seamounts: We mapped five previously explored seafloor features. An additional seven features may be sufficiently well mapped enough to name, by combining data from this expedition with existing data, in collaboration with the other expedition teams. Of twelve newly discovered features, nine new unexplored sea floor features are candidates for formal naming (proposals for formal naming for these seafloor features are in development; seamounts within the Chile EEZ around Rapa Nui have been submitted to the Koro Nui o te Vaikaiva to begin the process of proposing names), and three additional features require further exploration before naming proposals can be submitted. Additionally, one feature known to exist through historical publication (Parin et al 1997), but had not been formally named, was mapped. A naming proposal will be developed for this feature, taking into consideration its history. Finally, one named feature, Atlant, was mapped for the first time and was identified to be comprised of two features; which will be updated in GEBCO and a second name proposed for the other feature.

FKt240108/FKt240224 new species:

Since the expeditions, three workshops on species discovery in collaboration with Ocean Census have been conducted. To date, ≥ 144 potential new species in Asteroidea (15), Ophuroidea (30), Raphitomidae (12), Galatheoidea (40; one published), Echinoidea (5), Octocorallia (26), Scleractinia (5), Antipatharia (5), and Demospongidae (6) have been tentatively confirmed during these workshops. An additional ≥ 40 new species in Nudibranchia (10) and Hexactinellidae (30) have been identified. Numerous taxa are still awaiting review, so we anticipate exceeding the 200 count for potential new species we have identified. Although many species were sampled in both expeditions, we credit them to the first expedition in which a sample was collected.

Of the 184 potential new species reviewed to date, one has been described and published: a squat lobster named *Galathea tukitukimea*.

Citation: Gallardo Salamanca Maria de los Angeles, Asorey C, Macpherson E (2025) A new species of *Galathea* (Decapoda, Galatheidae) from the seamounts of the Easter Island area (Southeast Pacific Ocean Ridge) associated with a sea urchin. ZooKeys 1248: 111-123. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1248.159542>

Of the 144 new species tentatively confirmed at Ocean Census workshops, 17 species of Asteroidea, Raphitomidae, Scleractinia, and Octocorallia are described in manuscripts in preparation from these two expeditions; see below for which of the 17 correspond to FKt240108 and FKt240224. Among these species are two new genera of Asteroidea.

FKt240108: Three Asteroidea, one Raphitomidae, and one Scleractinia.

FKt240224: Eight Asteroidea, three Scleractinia, and one Galatheidae.

2.2.3 Software Utilized

- ArcGIS PRO (ESRI, Inc., Redlands, CA)
- Maxent (<https://github.com/mrmaxent/Maxent>)
- QGIS (QGIS.org, Open Source Geospatial Foundation. <https://qgis.org>)

- QPS Qimera (Zeist, Netherlands: QPS B.V. Retrieved from: <https://qps.nl/qimera/>)
- QPS Qinsy (Zeist, Netherlands: QPS B.V. Retrieved from <https://qps.nl/qinsy/>)
- QPS Fledermaus (Zeist, Netherlands: QPS B.V. Retrieved from <https://qps.nl/fledermaus/>)
- Global Mapper (Blue Marble Geographics. Available from <https://www.blumarblegeo.com/>)
- Geneious Prime 2025-2026 (Dotmatics, Auckland, NZ. Available from <https://www.geneious.com/>)
- DragonFly 3D World (Comet Technologies Canada Inc. Available from <https://dragonfly.comet.tech/>)
- The Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) at The University of Texas (Austin, TX, <https://tacc.utexas.edu/>)
- The University of Texas High-Resolution X-ray Computed Tomography Facility (UTCT, Austin, TX; <https://www.ctlab.geo.utexas.edu/>)
- MATLAB (The MathWorks Inc., Natick, MA. Available from <https://www.mathworks.com>)
- Trimmomatic package (Bolger et al. 2014)
- Illumiprocessor (Faircloth 2013)
- Phyluce v.1.7.3 (Faircloth 2015).
- SPAdes v. 4.2.0 (Bankevich et al. 2012; Prjibelski et al. 2020)
- Helicon Remote (Helicon Soft, Ltd., Kharkiv, Ukraine)
- Helicon Focus (Helicon Soft, Ltd., Kharkiv, Ukraine)
- Trim Galore 0.6.10 (Krueger et al. 2023)
- Seqtk-1.5 (Li 2025)
- MAFFT v. 7.475 (Kato and Standley 2013)
- Gblocks 0.91b (Talavera and Castresana 2007)
- IQ-tree 2.4.0/3.1.1 (Nguyen et al. 2015; Minh et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2025)
- ModelFinder with PartitionFinder (Lanfear et al. 2012; Chernomor et al. 2016)
- Sealog/Seacloud (SOI 2024; Pinner 2024)
- Microsoft Office
- Adobe Creative Cloud Applications (Adobe Inc. <https://www.adobe.com>)

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report’s publication date (Table 1).

Data Type	Curator	Status
Vessel underway data	FKt240108: Rolling Deck to Repository FKt240224: Rolling Deck to Repository	Completed
ADCP	FKt240108: University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Completed

Data Type	Curator	Status
	FKt240224: University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	
Processed Multibeam from <i>Falkor (too)</i>	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	In process
A provisional list of nematode species encountered	MeioChile	Completed
ROV <i>SuBastian</i> Sensor Data	FKt240108: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) FKt240224: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
Processed Multibeam from <i>Falkor (too)</i>	FKt240108: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) FKt240224: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	In process
ROV Image Data	FKt240108: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) FKt240224: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
ROV Event Log Data	FKt240108: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) FKt240224: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
Sample List	Zenodo	Completed
Oceanic and meteorological data	FKt240108: Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO) FKt240224: Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO)	In process
Nutrient data	FKt240108: PANGAEA FKt240224: PANGAEA	In process
Georeferenced taxonomic data	FKt240108: Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) FKt240224: Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)	In process
FKt240224 Acoustic data and outputs		
Model outputs	FKt240108: Habitat Suitability	In process

Data Type	Curator	Status
	FKt240224: Habitat Suitability	
Morphospecies lists	FKt240108: Zenodo FKt240224: Zenodo	Regularly updated
Genetic datasets from specimen collections and eDNA	FKt240108: Zenodo FKt240224: Zenodo	In process
Stable isotope data	FKt240108: Zenodo FKt240224: Zenodo	Completed
FKt240224 Ex situ experimental data		In process
FKt240224 M3 processed data		Insufficient quality for analysis
Fkt240108 / FKt240224 Biodiversity Data	NCBI	In progress

Table 1. List of all publicly available data

Additional datasets in progress include composition and abundance data of benthic macrofauna inhabiting sediments, with samples collected using push cores. It also includes sediment biogeochemistry data such as stable isotopes (C13 and N15), pH, redox potential, chlorophyll, pigments, granulometry, organic matter, organic carbon, and carbonates. Responsible person: Eulogio Soto

New species descriptions underway:

- Coelopleurus species (expected end 2026). Responsible persons: Ariadna Mecho, Jan Maximiliano Tapia-Guerra, Kirill Minin
- Corallidae species (expected end 2026). Responsible persons: Erin E Easton, Juan Sanchez
- Asteroidea species (expected 2026). Responsible persons: Ariadna Mecho, Chris Mah
- Ophiuroidea species (expected 2026). Responsible persons: Tim O'Hara, Javier Sellanes
- Plexauridae species (expected 2027). Responsible persons: Asako Matsumoto, Erin E Easton
- Raphitomidae species (expected 2026). Responsible persons: Javier Sellanes, Peter Stahlschmidt
- Galatheoidea species (expected 2026-2027). Responsible persons: Maria de los Angeles Gallardo-Salamanca, Enrique Macpherson
- Echinoidea species (expected 2026). Responsible persons: Ariadna Mecho, Kirill Minin
- Primnoidae species (expected 2027). Pedro Nascimiento, Marcelo Kitihara, Erin E Easton
- Octocorallia species (expected 2006 and beyond). Responsible persons: Erin E Easton, Juan Sanchez, Marcelo Kitihara, TBD

- Scleractinia species (expected 2026 and beyond). Responsible persons: Marcelo Kitihara, Erin E Easton
- Antipatharia species (expected 2027). Responsible persons: Erin E Easton, Tina Molodtsova
- Demospongidae (expected 2026-2027). Responsible persons: Javier Cristobo, Javier Sellanes
- Hexactinellidae (expected 2027). Responsible persons: Celso Domingos, Javier Sellanes
- Nudibranchidae (expected 2026). Responsible persons: Javier Sellanes, Alejandro Mendivil
- Fish species (expected 2027). Responsible persons: Jan M. Tapia-Guerra, Javier Sellanes, Erin E Easton, TBD

2.4 Publications

Oyanadel et al. (2025). Catálogo Ilustrado de Asteroideos del Parque Marino Nazca-Desventuradas.

Portflitt-Toro, M. (2025). Habitantes de las profundidades: Una exploración a los montes submarinos del Pacífico Sudeste. Universidad Católica del Norte.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17289608>

Tapia-Guerra, J. M., Sellanes, J., Gorny, M., Easton, E. E. (2025) First observations of filamentous cyanobacterial mats on whip black corals (Antipatharia: Stichopathes spp.) off Rapa Nui (Easter Island), Chile. Bulletin of Marine Science <https://doi.org/10.5343/bms.2024.0071>

Tapia-Guerra, J. M., Sellanes, J., Gorny, M., Easton, E. E. (2025) First observations of filamentous cyanobacterial mats on whip black corals (Antipatharia: Stichopathes spp.) off Rapa Nui (Easter Island), Chile. Bulletin of Marine Science <https://doi.org/10.5343/bms.2024.0071>.

Gaymer, C. F., Wagner, D., Alvarez-Varas, R., Boteler, B., Bravo, L., Brooks, C. M., Chavez-Molina, V., Currie, D., Delgado, J. P., Dewitte, B., Easton, E. E., Friedlander, A. M., Gallardo, M., Gianni, M., Gjerde, K., Gorny, M., Hormazábal, S., Hucke-Gaete, R., Luna-Jorquera, G., Mecho, A., Morales, N., Morgan, L., Nuñez, P., Ramos, M., Rapu, J., Rodrigo, C., Sellanes, J., Soto, E., Thiel, M., van der Meer, L., Veliz, D. (2025) Research advances and conservation needs for an effective protection of the Salas & Gómez and Nazca ridges: a natural and cultural heritage hotspot in the southeastern Pacific Ocean. Marine Policy, 171:106453.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106453>.

Troni, G., Rodríguez-Martínez, S., Savini, A., Micallef, A., Martin, E., Roberts, P., Fuentes, J., Sufán, V., "Exploring the Salas y Gómez Ridge: 3D Seafloor Mapping with Scalable Robotics," in R. Durán (Ed.), Geomorfología submarina, 2025, pp. 22–23, 259–261, ISBN: 978-84-1067-269-7.

Gallardo Salamanca MdelosÁngeles, Asorey C, Macpherson E (2025) A new species of Galathea (Decapoda, Galatheidæ) from the seamounts of the Easter Island area (Southeast Pacific Ocean Ridge) associated with a sea urchin. ZooKeys 1248: 111-123.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1248.159542>.

Carrasco SA, Ibáñez CM, Varela AI, Tapia-Guerra JM, Easton EE, Sellanes J. Morphology, Phylogeny and Distribution of Scaevargus (Cephalopoda: Octopoda) in Southeast Pacific Seamounts. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*. 2026; 14(7):678. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse14070678>.

Fernández-Zúñiga, M., et al. (2025). Spatial ecology of two emblematic deep-sea crustaceans in the Salas y Gómez, Nazca and Juan Fernández ridges Southeast Pacific. *Scientific Reports* 15(1): 14538. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-98820-4>.

In review / revision at time of report publication:

- Petit I., Tapia-Guerra, J.M., Gaymer, C.F., Castro-Contreras, M., Payá, I., Sellanes, J., Easton, E.E., Gallardo, M-A., Watling, L. (In review) Impacts of bottom trawling fishing in the Juan Fernández ridge, Chile. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*. (Submitted December 2025)
- Niyazi, Y., Swanborn, D. J. B., Tapia-Guerra, J. M., Sellanes, J., Easton, E. E., Zapata-Hernández, G., Stewart, H. A., Jamieson, A. J. Automated and quantitative characterization of multi-scale benthic habitat and associated biological communities of an unknown southeast Pacific seamount. *PLOS One*. (Submitted 9 March 2026) <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.64898/2026.03.11.710978v1.full>
- Gaymer, C. F., Petit, I., Canales, C., Sanchez, N., Sellanes, J., Easton, E. E., Chavez-Molina, V., Friedlander, A., Wagner, D. (In review). Salas y Gómez and Nazca ridges: the need for protection, with a minimum impact on fishing activities. *Ocean and Coastal Management* (Submitted 6 March 2026) https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=6478678
- Mecho, A., Tapia-Guerra, J. M., Sellanes, J., Ketter, T., Easton, E. E. (In revision) First *in situ* observations of the understudied family Octacnemidae (Ascidiacea) in the Southeast Pacific. *Bulletin of Marine Science*. (Submitted 23 October 2024; minor revisions needed 10 July 2025 – new genetic data is being included, so delayed)
- Tapia-Guerra, J. M., Sellanes, J., Ketter, T., Easton, E. E. (In revision) First *in situ* observations of Rhizophysidae Brandt, 1835 siphonophores in the South Pacific. *Bulletin of Marine Science*. (Submitted 27 July 2024; major revisions requested – awaiting genetic data)
- Flores EA, Gallardo MA, Ramos M, Asorey CM, Pizarro-Koch M, Hammond ML, Tapia JM, Bravo L, Gaymer CF, Véliz D, Sellanes J. Connectivity pathways of the jagged lobster *Projasus bahamondei*: oceanic hubs and transport barriers in the Southeast Pacific.
- Amenábar, M, Cornejo D-Ottone, M, Llanillo, PJ, Hormazábal, S, Hidalgo, P, Soto, EH, Easton, EE, Esquete, P, Marlow, JJ. Nitrous oxide as a non-conservative tracer of water masses revealing biogeochemical dynamics in the Humboldt Current System. *Progress in Oceanography* (Submitted 14 April 2026)
- Sánchez, JA, Easton, EE, Garcia, N, Román-Ochoa, Y, Cáceres, JK, Sellanes, J. A new chitin-contained bubblegum corals (Paragorgia: Corallidae) from the Nazca Ridge: the mystery of skeleton-less branching octocorals revealed. *Scientific Reports* (Submitted 5 June 2026) <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-9945280/v1>
- Diaz, C, Pérez-Rosales, G, Laverick, J, Hernandez, A, RadiceV, Doherty, M, Adjeroud, M, Argyle, P, Carr, M, Barshis, D, Bongaerts, P, Brival, A, Cabaitan, P., Clegg, L, Colin, P, Debuysse, J, Denis, V, Easton, EE, Engelbert, N, Eyal, G, Goodbody, G, Harii, S, Hoarau, L, Hosegood, P, Johan, O, Krampnitz, N, Maida, M, Morejohn, K, Morgan, K,

Ferreira, B, Parrish, M, penin, L, Pérez, M, Pichon, M, Rachmawati, R, Rocha, L, Rouzé, H, Samimi-Namin, K, Sinniger, F, Smith, T, stefanoudis, P, Wyatt, A, Foster, N. Beneath the surface of the 2023-25 Global Coral Bleaching Event: depth, thermal stress and local variability. *Science* (submitted 23 June 2026)

- Gallardo-Salamanca, MA, Rodríguez-Flores, PC, Macpherson, E.. Squat lobsters of the family Munidopsidae Ortmann, 1898 (Decapoda, Galatheaidea) from the seamounts of the Southeast Pacific Ocean Ridges. *Zoosystematics and Evolution*. (Submitted 14 April 2026)

3 Appendix

3.1 Science Party Information

Scientist	Institution
Erin Easton	University of Texas Rio Grande Valley
Maria de Los Angeles Gallardo	Universidad Católica del Norte
Paige Maroni	University of Western Australia
Elyssia Gonzalez	University of Texas Rio Grande Valley
Javier Sellanes	Universidad Católica del Norte
Maritza Castro	Universidad Católica del Norte
Jorge Perez	Museo Nacional de Historia Natural de Chile
German Zapata	Universidad Católica del Norte
Pablo Fajardo	Juan Fernandez Islands
Francisca Oyanadel	Universidad Católica del Norte
Eulogio Soto	Universidad de Valparaíso
Jan Tapia	Universidad Católica del Norte
Celso Domingos	CIIMAR - Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research
Yakup Niyazi	University of Western Australia
Bernardita Mutschke	Universidad de Valparaíso
Macarena Pozo	Universidad Católica del Norte
Nicolas Luna	Universidad Católica del Norte
Cynthia Antinao Denmark	Universidad de Valparaíso
Esteban Quevedo	Universidad Católica del Norte
Marco Perez	Juan Fernandez Islands
Alessandra Savini	University of Milano-Bicocca
Ariadna Mecho	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
Bastian Riveros	Universidad Católica del Norte
Brian Kennedy	Independent
Claudia Berardi	Municipality of Rapa Nui
Emilia Palma Tuki	Municipality of Rapa Nui
Fernando Angel Fernandez-Alvarez	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

Scientist	Institution
Gaspar Felipe Gonzalez Morales	National Department of State Borders and Boundaries (DIFROL)
Giancarlo Troni	MBARI
Jan Maximiliano Fernando Tapia Guerra	Universidad Católica del Norte
Javeira Fuentes	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile
Josefa Araya	Universidad Católica del Norte
Luca Fallati	University of Milano-Bicocca
Marcela Hey	Municipality of Rapa Nui
Martiza Fernanda Castro Contreras	Universidad Católica del Norte
Matias Portflitt	Universidad Católica del Norte
Matthew Lee	Universidad de Los Lagos
Megan Francis	University of Texas Rio Grande Valley
Rosanne Dodde	Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)
Sebastian Rodriguez	MBARI
Vicente Sufan	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile
Yerko Castillo	University of Valparaíso

Table 2. List of scientists and students aboard *Falkor (too)*.

3.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

Conference presentation (Poster): Tapia-Guerra JM. et al., (2026). Explorando el océano profundo: diversidad bentónica y hábitats de los montes submarinos de las dorsales de Nazca y Salas & Gómez (2026). XLV Congreso de Ciencias del Mar. Concepción, Chile.

Conference presentation (Poster): Lee M., Soto E., Easton EE. (2026). Primera observación de Loricifera en los montes submarinos del Pacífico Sudeste. (2026). XLV Congreso de Ciencias del Mar. Concepción, Chile.

Conference presentation (Oral): Fallati L., Easton E., Bellotti P., Paglia S., Tapia-Guerra JM., Sellanes J., Troni J., Micallef A., Savini A. (2026). Morphological and Habitat Mapping of Seamounts and Guyots along the Salas y Gómez Ridge. 11th IAG International Conference on Geomorphology. Christchurch, New Zealand

Conference presentation (Oral): Tapia-Guerra JM., Easton EE., Sellanes J. et al. (2026). Caracterización multiescala del monte submarino Solito: un ecosistema único de alto valor para la conservación. XLV Congreso de Ciencias del Mar, Concepción, Chile.

Conference presentation (Oral): Domingos C., Sellanes J., Easton EE., Despujois DJ. (2026). Riqueza e potencial de novas espécies de esponjas em montes submarinos do Pacífico Sudeste. 3º Simpósio Brasileiro de Espongologia, Salvador Bahía, Brasil.

Conference presentation (Poster): Lee M., Soto E., Easton EE. (2025). A new species of marine tardigrade *Actinarctus* sp. nov. from a seamount of the Salas y Gómez Ridge, southeastern Pacific Ocean. XLIV Congreso de Ciencias del Mar. Viña del Mar, Chile

Conference presentation (Oral): Lee M., Soto E., Easton EE. (2025). Variaciones en las comunidades de nematodos de vida libre en los montes submarinos del Pacífico sureste. XLIV Congreso de Ciencias del Mar. Viña del Mar, Chile

Conference presentation (Oral): Portflitt-Toro M., Luna N., Luna-Jorquera G. (2025). Distribución y abundancia de aves marinas en las dorsales de Salas y Gómez, Nazca y Juan Fernández. XLIV Congreso de Ciencias del Mar. Viña del Mar, Chile

Conference presentation (Oral). Dodde, R.S. (2025). Squatlantis: Setting physiological baselines in the seamounts of the South East Pacific using new records of squat lobsters. 17th DSBS congress in Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong.

Ship to Shore: Easton, E.E. (2025) Schmidt Ocean Institute Ship-to-Shore to South Texas Ecotourism Center and UTRGV Coastal Studies Laboratory. South Padre Island, Texas, USA.

Oral presentation. Easton, E. E. (2025) Brain and Beyond: Southeast Pacific Seamounts - Exploration and Discovery. UTRGV School of Medicine Brain and Beyond Seminar Series, Virtual.

Conference presentation (Oral): Gallardo, M.A.* (2025). Oceanic island, Nazca and Salas & Gómez ridges: New frontiers for new questions. In: The Chilean sea: a natural laboratory for biodiversity and other challenger. COP16, Chile Pavilion-Blue zone, Calí, Colombia.

Invited speaker presentation: Gallardo, M.A.* (2025). Exploring the depths of the seamounts of southeast Pacific: a world to discover. Congreso del Futuro, La Serena, Chile.

Workshop presentation (Oral): Troni G., Rodríguez-Martínez S., Martin E., Roberts P., Fuentes-Guiñez J. and Barnard K. (2025). On the Development of a Portable and Cost-Effective Multimodal Imaging System for Underwater Mapping and Monitoring with Remotely Operated Vehicles. International Conference on Robotics and Automation - Workshop on Field Robotics, Atlanta, Georgia, USA.

Conference Presentation (Poster): Niyazi Y., Swanborn DJB., Tapia-Guerra JM., Stewart HA., Jamieson AJ., Easton EE., Sellanes J. (2025). Quantitative characterization of geomorphology and deep-sea benthic habitats of a newly identified isolated seamount in the Southeastern Pacific. Marine Geological and Biological Habitat Mapping (GeoHab), Key West, Florida, USA.

Conference Presentation (Poster): Sanguinetti G., Easton EE., Tapia-Guerra JM., Sellanes J. (2025). Contribución al conocimiento de la ictiofauna demersal y bentónica asociada a los montes submarinos del Parque Marino Motu Motiro Hiva, Chile. Congreso de Ciencias del Mar, Montemar, Viña del Mar, Chile.

Conference Presentation (Oral): Magna V., Tapia-Guerra JM., Sellanes J., Easton EE. (2025). Caracterización ecológica y ampliación del patrón de distribución de la familia Macrouridae en las dorsales de Nazca y Salas y Gómez. Congreso de Ciencias del Mar, Montemar, Viña del Mar, Chile.

Conference presentation (Poster): Mecho A., Tapia-Guerra JM., Sellanes J., Ketter T., Easton EE. (2024). Nuevos registros y primeras observaciones in situ de tunicados carnívoros: la poco

conocida familia Octacnemidae (Asciidiacea) en el Pacífico Sudeste. 1er Congreso Chileno de Zoología. Universidad Católica del Maule (UCM), Talca, Chile.

Conference presentation (Oral). Portflitt-Toro M., Sellanes J., Easton E., Gaymer C., Nolan H., Havens A., & Pesternikova S. (2024). Conectándose desde los montes submarinos del Pacífico Sudeste: experiencia de comunicación y divulgación. IV Encuentro Nacional de Profesionales de la Comunicación y Divulgación de la Ciencia, Tecnología, Conocimiento e Innovación, PUCV, Valparaíso, Chile.

Guest presentation (Oral). Dodde, R.S., Gallardo-Salamanca, M., Pozo, M., Rivieros Flores, B.I., Erin, E.E., Wurz, E., Osinga, R., Reichart, G., Sellanes, J., (2024). Squatlantis: Setting physiological baselines in the seamounts of the South East Pacific using new records of squat lobsters. Aquarium and Museum at FCM-UCN. Coquimbo, Chile.

Guest presentation (Oral). Dodde, R.S., Gallardo-Salamanca, M., Pozo, M., Rivieros Flores, B.I., Erin, E.E., Wurz, E., Osinga, R., Reichart, G., Sellanes, J., (2024). An internship considering crustaceans. Marine Life course for first year Marine Scientists, Wageningen University & Research. Wageningen, The Netherlands.

Internship presentation (Oral). Dodde, R.S., Gallardo-Salamanca, M., Pozo, M., Rivieros Flores, B.I., Erin, E.E., Wurz, E., Sellanes, J., (2024). Squatlantis: Setting physiological baselines in the seamounts of the South East Pacific using new records of squat lobsters. Final internship presentation for the chairgroup Marine animal ecology. Wageningen, the Netherlands.

Guest presentation (Oral). Dodde, R.S.(2024). Diepgang; de diepzee en zijn inwoners. Presented at the annual congress of the Dutch Nature Youth Association (NJN). Oud-Leusden (Leusden), Netherlands.

Oral presentation: Easton, E.E. (2024). Post-cruise presentation report to Koro Nui o te Vaikava. Virtual.

Oral presentation: Easton, E.E. (2024). Resumen del crucero a los montes submarinos inexplorados de la cordillera de Sala y Gómez. Public presentation at the Universidad Católica del Norte Acuario y Museo, Coquimbo, Chile.

Oral presentation: Easton, E.E. (2024). Preliminary findings from exploration of the Nazca and Salas y Gómez ridges and integrative octocoral systematics. Invited seminar at Texas A&M – Galveston, Galveston, TX, USA.

Invited presentation: Easton, E.E. (2024). Nazca and Salas y Gómez ridges: discoveries with student and community engagement. UTRGV Convocation in Brownsville and Edinburg. Brownsville, Texas, USA

Invited presentation: Easton, E.E. (2024) Southeast Pacific Seamounts: Recent Discoveries and Community Engagement with an Update on Progress. DOSI-led Seamount Science Summit: "Global Scientific Perspectives for Integrating Science into Policy," Honolulu, Hawaii, USA.

Poster presentation: Francis, M., Tapia-Guerra, J.M., González-Soto, M., Easton, E.E. (2024). Assessing the distribution of *Leptoseria* across varying depths throughout the seamounts of the Salas y Gómez Ridge. UTRGV COS Annual Research Conference. South Padre Island, TX, USA.

Oral Presentation: Gaymer C.F., Petit I., Sellanes J., Easton E., Canales C., Sanchez N., Tapia-Guerra J., Paredes F., Rodriguez H. (2024). Salas y Gómez and Nazca ridges: the need for protection, with a minimum impact on fisheries. 12th Meeting of the Scientific Committee. Lima, Perú.

Poster presentation: González-Soto, M, Cornejo-D'Ottone, M., Easton E.E. (2024). Caracterización Oceanográfica de la transecta Valparaíso- Rapa Nui (25°S) durante el Crucero FKt240224, verano Austral 2024. XLIII Congreso Ciencias, Concepción, Chile. Poster presentation.

Guest Presentation (Oral): Jan Tapia Guerra, Maritza Castro, Javier Sellanes & Erin Easton. (2024). A comprehensive review of the megafauna in the seamounts. Primer congreso de Zoología en Chile. Talca, Chile.

Guest presentation (Oral): Lee, M.R.* (2024) LOS MONTES SUBMARINOS DEL PACÍFICO SUDESTE. Una expedición a bordo del *Falkor (too)*. Presentation to the students of the undergraduate Marine Biology program at the Universidad de Los Lagos. Centro i~mar, Universidad de Los Lagos, Puerto Montt, Chile.

Conference presentation (Oral): Mecho A* (2024) SALAS Y GOMEZ RIDGE BLUE CORRIDOR (CHILE-HIGH SEAS). Marine Protected Areas Forum: Progress, Obstacles and Solutions. UN Ocean Decade Conference, Barcelona, Spain.

Conference presentation (Poster): Mecho A.*, Tapia-Guerra J.M.**, Sellanes J.*, Ketter T., Easton E.E.* (2024). Nuevos registros y primeras observaciones in situ de tunicados carnívoros: la poco conocida familia Octacnemidae (Ascidacea) en el Pacífico Sudeste. 1er Congreso Chileno de Zoología, Talca, Chile.

3.3 Student Projects, Thesis, and Dissertations

Master's internship: Dodde, R.S., Gallardo-Salamanca, M., Pozo, M., Rivieros Flores, B.I., Erin, E.E., Wurz, E., Sellanes, J., (2024). Squatlantis: Setting physiological baselines in the seamounts of the South East Pacific using new records of squat lobsters. Final Internship report.

Supervisors: E. Wurz and Maria de los Angeles Gallardo Salamanca. Completed 2024.

Master's thesis: Mazzarino Filippo, Geomorphological mapping of Pacific seamounts and guyots of the Salas y Gomez Ridge – Marine Geology at University of Milano-Bicocca.

Supervisors: Alessandra Savini and Luca Fallati. Ongoing

Master's thesis: Silvia Paglia, Geomorphological mapping of Pacific seamounts and guyots of the Salas y Gomez Ridge. Master's thesis in Marine Geology at University of Milano-Bicocca.

Supervisors: Alessandra Savini and Luca Fallati. Completed 2025

Master's thesis: Bellotti Pietro, Analysis of Multibeam Dataset for interpreting the origin and evolution of seamounts and guyots (Salas y Gomez Ridge, Pacific Ocean) - Master's thesis in Marine Geology at University of Milano-Bicocca. **Supervisors:** Alessandra Savini and Luca Fallati. Completed 2025

Master's thesis: Anna Maria Castigli, Characterization of seafloor geomorphology and abiotic components of seamounts and guyots along the Salas y Gómez Ridge in the southeastern Pacific Ocean - Master's thesis in Marine Sciences at University of Milano-Bicocca. **Supervisors:** Alessandra Savini and Luca Fallati. Completed 2026

Bachelor's thesis: Francisca Oyanadel (2025). Taxonomic revision and ecological aspects of the asteroids (echinodermata) of the seamounts and oceanic islands of the Nazca-Desventuradas marine park, Chile. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisors:** Javier Sellanes, Jan M. Tapia Guerra. Completed 2025.

Bachelor's thesis: Bernardita Mutschke. Characterization of macroinfaunal communities and biogeochemical parameters of the seamounts of the Nazca Ridge, Desventuradas Islands, and Juan Fernández Ridge. Universidad de Valparaíso. **Supervisor:** Eulogio Soto. Completed 2025.

Bachelor's thesis: Yerko Castillo. Characterization of macrobenthic communities of soft-bottom habitats and associated biogeochemistry of seamounts from the Salas y Gómez Ridge in the southeastern Pacific Ocean. Universidad de Valparaíso. **Supervisor:** Eulogio Soto. Completed 2025.

Undergraduate Student Experience internship: Megan Francis Annotation of FKt240224 videos and analysis of *Leptoseris* distribution. The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley. **Supervisor:** Erin E Easton. In progress.

Postdoctoral research: Ignacia Petit. Impact of fisheries on southeast Pacific seamounts. **Supervisor:** Carlos F. Gaymer

Doctoral dissertation: Jan M. Tapia-Guerra. Characterization of the benthic habitats and communities of the oceanic islands and seamounts of the Salas y Gómez and Nazca ridges. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisors:** Javier Sellanes and Erin E Easton. In progress.

Bachelor's thesis: Bastian Riveros. Taxonomic revision of *Phylladorhynchus* (Crustacea: Anomura: Galatheidea) found in southeast Pacific oceanic islands. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Javier Sellanes and Maria de los Angeles Gallardo Salamanca. Completed 2024.

Bachelor's thesis: Maritza Castro. First ecological characterization of sea pens (Octocorallia: Pennatuloidae) of the Nazca-Desventuradas Marine Park. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Jan M. Tapia Guerra and Javier Sellanes. Completed 2024.

Bachelor's thesis: Francisca Oyandadel. Revision and ecological aspects of the seastars (Echinodermata: Asteroidea) of the oceanic islands and seamounts of the Nazca-Desventuradas Marine Park. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Jan M. Tapia Guerra and Javier Sellanes. Completed 2025.

Bachelor's thesis: Ignacio Diaz Flores. Mesophotic ichthyofauna of the Rapa Nui Marine Protected Area. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Javier Sellanes. Completed 2024.

Bachelor's thesis: Guiseppe Sanguinetti. Characterization of the ichthyofauna of the Motu Motiro Hiva Marine Park. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Javier Sellanes. In progress.

Bachelor's thesis: Rodrigo Orellana. Nazca-Desventuradas Marine Park: Description of a biogeographic transition-zone indicator species, *Miersiella* sp. (Crustacea: Brachyura). Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Maria de los Angeles Gallardo-Salamanca. In progress.

Bachelor's thesis: Ignacio Díaz Godoy. Characterization of the family Chaunacidae of the Salas y Gómez and Nazca ridges. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Jan M. Tapia-Guerra and Javier Sellanes. Completed 2026.

Bachelor's thesis: Jehieli Ocayo Ocaranza. Relationship between the corals and squat lobsters in the Salas y Gómez and Nazca ridges. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Maria de los Angeles Gallardo-Salamanca. In progress.

Bachelor's thesis: Vicente Magna. Characterization of the Macrouridae of the Salas y Gómez and Nazca ridges. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Jan M. Tapia-Guerra and Javier Sellanes. Completed 2026.

Bachelor's thesis: Romina Tello. Environmental factors structuring the communities of Demospongiae y Hexactinellida on the seamount Solito. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Javier Sellanes. In progress.

Bachelor's internship: Monserratt Gonzalez Soto. Oceanographic patterns of the Salas y Gómez Ridge. Universidad de Valparaíso. **Supervisor:** Erin E Easton. Completed 2024.

Bachelor's thesis: Javiera Solis. Paisajes sonoros de Ecosistemas de Corales Mesofóticos (MCEs) de *Leptoseris* spp. sanos y degradados en la isla Rapa Nui. Universidad Católica del Norte. **Supervisor:** Javier Sellanes. In progress.

3.4 Cruise Records

- FKt240108
 - [Cruise Logs](#)
 - [Cruise Vlogs](#)
 - [ROV Subastian Dive List](#)
- FKt240224
 - [ROV SuBastian Dive List](#)

3.5 Media

Awards

Explorers Club 2025 Citation of Merit to Chief Scientists Erin E Easton and Javier Sellanes with the Schmidt Ocean Institute for co-leading the international team that discovered over 150 new species in the southeast Pacific seamounts. <https://www.explorers.org/2025-ecad-awardees/>

2025 College of Sciences (The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley) Excellence in Research, Scholarship, or Creative Activity Award to Erin E Easton.

Media Reports, Radio, and News in Chile

Lee, M.R.*, 7th of May 2024, “Investigador del Centro i~mar ULagos participa en exitoso buque científico que descubrió nuevas especies para la ciencia”. Osorno En Vivo.

Lee, M.R.*, 7th of May 2024, “Investigador del Centro i~mar ULagos participa en exitoso buque científico que descubrió nuevas especies para la ciencia”. Radio Antillanca.

Lee, M.R.*, 8th of May 2024, “Centro i~mar ULagos a bordo de exitoso buque científico que descubrió nuevas especies para la ciencia”. Aqua

Lee, M.R.*, 8th of May 2024, “Investigador de la ULagos participa en expedición que descubrió nuevas especies para la ciencia”. El Austral – El Diario de Osorno

Lee, M.R.*, 8th of May 2024, “Investigadore del Centro i~mar ULagos participa en exitosos buque científico”. Muno Acuicola.

Lee, M.R.*, 9th of May 2024, “Investigador del Centro i~mar ULagos participa en exitoso buque científico que descubrió nuevas especies para la ciencia”. G5 Noticias.

Lee, M.R.*, 9th of May 2024 “Investigador del Centro i~mar ULagos participa en exitoso buque científico que descubrió nuevas especies para la ciencia”. Noticias Chiloé.

[RTVE Play](#) media coverage

Media Reports, Radio, and News in the Netherlands

Dodde R. , university paper, Resource Wageningen University and Research, WUR-student vindt nieuwe soorten in Chili - Resource online (resource-online.nl)10-05-202410-05-2024.<https://edepot.wur.nl/658530>

Media Reports, Radio, and News in Spain

Mecho A*, RTVE – Programa Objetivo Planeta presentado por Lorenzo Milá -

<https://www.rtve.es/play/videos/objetivo-planeta/viaje-fondo-del-mar/16096544/>

<https://www.ccma.cat/3cat/un-equip-internacional-de-cientifics-descobreix-50-noves-especies-marines-a-xile/video/6276064/>

Mecho A*, Cadena Ser - <https://cadenaser.com/audio/1713092536522/>

Mecho A*, Entrevista Cadena Ser- Vall de Uxó:

<https://elcafedepipa.com/index.php/2024/12/09/podcast-la-biologa-de-xilxes-ariadna-mecho-ha-rebut-el-premi-mujeres-a-seguir-en-la-categoria-de-ciencia/>

Mecho A*, Onda Cero (interview at 01h:49m)-

https://www.ondacero.es/podcast/programas/gente-viajera/gente-viajera-05042026_2026040569d256bdf391850007f4904f.html

Press: La Vanguardia -

<https://www.lavanguardia.com/natural/20240411/9592983/descubiertas-mas-50-especies-submarinas-zonas-mas-inexploradas-planeta.html>

Press: El País - <https://elpais.com/clima-y-medio-ambiente/2024-04-13/la-investigadora-espanola-que-descubre-nuevas-especies-marinas-a-1500-metros-de-profundidad-en-chile.html>

Press: <https://efeverde.com/nuevas-especies-submarinas-costas-chile/>

Press: <https://murciaplaza.com/cientificos-hallan-50-nuevas-especies-en-zonas-submarinas-poco-exploradas>

Press: <https://www.europapress.es/catalunya/noticia-grupo-coliderado-bsc-halla-50-nuevas-especies-zonas-submarinas-poco-exploradas-20240411151025.html>

Press: https://www.diarimes.com/es/actualidad/240411/descubren-50-nuevas-especies-submarinas-zonas-inexploradas-planeta_143230.html

Press: El Punt Avui - <https://www.elpuntavui.cat/societat/article/15-ciencia/2406165-un-equip-liderat-per-una-investigadora-del-bsc-descobreix-mes-de-50-noves-especies-submarines.html>

Press: El Español - https://www.lespanol.com/invertia/disruptores/grandes-actores/investigacion/20250209/ariadna-mecho-premiada-biologa-fusiona-exploracion-submarina-supercomputacion-frenar-cambio-climatico/921658072_0.html

PierNEXT Innovation by Pier de Barcelona. “Nuevas especies, el potencial aún sin explorar de los océanos”. 19-04-2024. Link: <https://piernext.portdebarcelona.cat/entorno/nuevas-especies-el-potencial-aun-sin-explorar-de-los-oceanos/> [Spanish]

Allegra Rosenberg, The Long Now Foundation. “A Stream Flowing From The Sea”. 18-07-2024. Link: <https://longnow.org/ideas/a-stream-flowing-from-the-sea/> [English]

3.6 Community Outreach

Friday 7 June 2024 marked the opening of the temporary exhibition "Descubriendo nuestro océano profundo" in the name of the día mundial de los océanos 2024 in the Museo Marítimo Nacional. The opening was made by the Chilean Minister of Foreign Affairs, senator Lagos-Weber, the Chancellor of UCN and the Commander in Chief of the Chilean Navy. This exhibit was made in collaboration with the Foreign Affairs Ministry, as part of its strategy to disseminate the importance of the ridges for global conservation strategies. More than 15.000 people saw the exhibit.

During the Feria del Mar in Coquimbo, Serafina Moulton came and shared about the cruise at the Aquarium and Museum at FCM-UCN, including about her culture, sharing a hokko with more than 100 kids from different schools. She did this 7-10 May 2024 .

https://www.instagram.com/p/C6oYx2zuIHj/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRlODBiNWFlZA==

On January 24th, 2025, the documentary *Te Moana Ora* (The Living Ocean), directed by Claudia Berardi and Coca Sepúlveda, premiered in Rapa Nui with additional showing since then (Table 3). The film follows Serafina Moulton, a member of the Rapa Nui delegation on the expedition, and was screened at the Nayara Hanga Roa Hotel, where local authorities and community members filled the cinema hall. You can watch the trailer [here](#). The film was selected as part of

the 2025 Science Film Festival (October 1 and December 20, 2025), which reached over 950,000 viewers across 20 countries ([Festival Report 2025](#)).

Showing Date	Venue	Attendees/Views	Event Link	Version
24 January 2025	Nayara Hanga Roa Hotel, Rapa Nui, Chile	70 people		Spanish
26-28 January 2025	YouTube	3183 views in 48 hrs		Spanish, English
8 February 2025	Tapati Rapa Nui Festival	2500 people aprox		Spanish
9 June 2025	4th UN Ocean Conference, Nice, France	100 people aprox		English
24 September 2025	Municipality of Coquimbo, Chile	750 people aprox		Spanish
10 March 2026	Juno House, Barcelona, Spain	20 people		Spanish
Tbd May 2026	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	Open to all workers		Spanish

Table 3. Showing of *Te Moana Ora*

Additional Community Presentations:

- Mecho, A. (2025). 'Els Misteris de les Profunditats Marines' - open to all people. Xilxes, Spain.
- Mecho, A. (2025). The Unexplored Ocean – Outreach at Benigasló High-School. Vall de Uxó, Spain.
- Easton, E.E. (2025) Post-cruise presentation report to Koro Nui o te Vaikava. Hanga Roa, Chile.
- Easton, E.E. (2025) Post-cruise accomplishments to Rapa Nui community. Hanga Roa, Chile.
- Easton, E.E. (2025) Schmidt Ocean Institute Ship-to-Shore to South Texas Ecotourism Center and UTRGV Coastal Studies Laboratory. South Padre Island, Texas, USA.
- Easton, E.E. (2024) Post-cruise presentation report to Koro Nui o te Vaikava. Virtual.
- Taller Protección de Salas y Gómez and Nazca: preparación de estrategia científica y política desde Chile para South Pacific Regional Fisheries Management Organization.

Organiza: Oceana Chile y Coral Reef in the High Seas Coalition (CRHSC). Santiago, Chile.

- Working session dinner at 12th SC SPRMFO, 1 October 2024. Lima, Peru.
- Some of the cruise results were mentioned in the National Geographic Society's September 2024 issue, which dedicated two pages to researchers and specifically mentioned Chaunacops and an Uroptychus squat lobster (which is now a Sternostyliidae).

Local outreach

PierNEXT Innovation by Pier de Barcelona. "[Nuevas especies, el potencial aún sin explorar de los océanos](#)", 19 April 2024.

Allegra Rosenberg, The Long Now Foundation. "[A Stream Flowing From The Sea](#)", 18 July 2024.

October 3, 2025: Official launch of the illustrated popular science book "Habitantes de las profundidades: Una exploración a los montes submarinos del Pacífico Sudeste" (ed. M. Portflitt Toro and MA. Gallardo, ESMOI-UCN) at the Ex Congreso Nacional, Santiago, Chile. The launch was supported by the Senate of Chile and NGO Oceana, attended by senators, government officials from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and ANID, regional representatives of Rapa Nui and Valparaíso, NGOs, academics, and the general public. The book was recognized by the Vice President of the Senate, Senator Ricardo Lagos Weber, for its scientific quality and contribution to Chile's BBNJ Treaty efforts. Available in print and digital format (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17289608).

October 24, 2025 (Noche de Museos): Exhibition of samples and 3D-printed replicas of marine organisms obtained through the BiodUCCT project and the Falkor (too) expeditions, held at the UCN Coquimbo Aquarium (~400 attendees). Organized by J. Sellanes.

During 2024–2025, BiodUCCT researchers (ESMOI-UCN) made 85+ appearances in national and international media outlets reporting on the expeditions' discoveries and conservation impact. A full list is available in the Anillo BiodUCCT ATE220044 Final Report (2025).

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